

Development And Validation of Rp-Hplc Method For Estimation of Dapagliflozin In Bulk and Pharmaceutical Dosage Form

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ABSTRACT

Dapagliflozin is a novel inhibitor of renal sodium-glucose cotransporter 2, which allows an insulin-independent approach to improve Type-II diabetes hyperglycemia. It is a C-aryl glucoside derivative and is chemically known as (1s)-1, 5-anhydro-1-C-[4-chloro3-[(4-ethoxyphenyl) methyl] phenyl]-D- glucitol. Empirical formula is C₂₁H₂₅ClO₆ and has a molecular weight of 408.9g/mol. The present study indicates a simple, accurate, and precise reverse phase high performance liquid chromatography was developed and validated for the estimation of Dapagliflozin in pharmaceutical dosage form. The mobile phase used was Acetonitrile :Water 75:25v/v. The specifications of the chromatographic system are column C18 (Dimensions: 4.6 x 250 mm), flow rate 1ml/min, detection 285nm and injection volume 10ul and run time 5 min. The retention time was found 3.32min. The linearity curve was in the range of 20-70ppm. The recoveries found to be 96.75 to 103.43 %. The proposed method was validated and successfully applied to the estimation of Dapagliflozin and its dosage form.

Keywords: RP-HPLC, Dapagliflozin, Analytical Method Development, antihyperglycemic activity.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, research in analytical chemistry has concerned mainly on the development and application of physical and physicochemical analytical methods, instrumental analysis, in which their speed and sensitivity have far surpassed the classical methods of gravimetric and volumetric analysis. Almost all researchers have been supported by analytical techniques. Analytical methods have been improved by the progress of the analytical instruments based on the physical measurement supported by the electronics. Many Nobel prizes of chemistry and physics were given to the investigations of new method of analytical measurement. The goal of analytical measurement is to achieve high sensitivity and selectivity Analytical Chemistry deals with methods for determining the chemical composition of samples of matter.

A qualitative method yields information about the identity of atomic or molecular species or the functional groups in the sample; a quantitative method, in contrast, provides numerical information as to the relative amount of one or more of these components. Currently, Instrumental analysis is based on comparison of the signal from the sample with that from standard. Analytical chemistry encompasses chemical analysis, separation chemistry and instrumental analysis, including analytical methods and techniques.

Classification of Analytical Methods:

Analytical Chemistry consists of Qualitative analysis and Quantitative analysis.

- Qualitative analysis deals with the identification of elements, ions or compounds Present in the sample.

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• Quantitative analysis deals with determination of how much of one or more constituent is present.

Qualitative analysis is subdivided in to following classical methods (Figure No. 1)

Figure No. 1. Classification of Classical Methods.

Classical Methods:

In the early years of chemistry, most analyses were carried out through classical methods by separating components of interest in a sample by precipitation, extraction, or distillation. For quantitative analysis, the separated components were then treated with reagents that yielded products that could be recognized by their colors, boiling points or melting points, their solubility in a series of solvents, their odours, their optical activities, or their measurable physical properties.

a) Volumetric Methods:

It is also known as titrimetric method and is preferred over gravimetry due to speed and convenience. In Volumetric methods, assay is based on volume measurement of known solution strength that is required to react completely with the substance to be analysed. Depending upon type of reaction involved this

method is further classified as a) Neutralisation titration b) non-aqueous titration c) Precipitation titration d) Complexometric titration e) Redox titration

b) Gravimetric Methods: Gravimetric analysis is quantitative analysis by weight and process of isolating the weighing compound of known composition.

c) Gasometrical Method: This method involves measurement of volume of gas-by-gas burettes or nitro meters. They measure the volume of the gas liberated in the given chemical reaction and volume decreased of gas in present of adsorbing agent under standard condition of temperature and pressure. Quantitative analysis can be classified from different points of view based on the nature of material under examination, type of method employed, and the amount of desired constituent in sample material. Quantitative Analysis is further classified into:

Figure No. 2. Classification of Quantitative Analysis.

5.1 Equipment/Instruments Used:

Table No. 2. Equipment's and Instruments used

Sr.No.	Components	Details
1	Volumetric flask	Glass, Class-A
2	Beakers	Glass, Class-A
3	Measuring cylinders	Glass, Class-A
4	Volumetric pipettes	Glass, Class-A (both bulb and graduated)
5	Balance	Balance with sensitivity of 0.001 gm, Contech India
6	Water bath	Digital Temperature Controller, Bio-Technics, India
7	Column	Column C18 (Dimensions : 4.6 x 250 mm)
8	HPLC system	Shimadzu Model : DGU-20A5R (P-Series) Detector : PDA CAT. NO.: 228-65555-58 SERIAL NO.: L227359551 US

5.1 Reagents, Standards and Samples:

5.1.1 Reagents:

Table No. 3. Reagent Used

Sr.No.	Reagent	Grade	Make
1	Acetonitrile	HPLC grade	Research Lab, Mumbai
2	Methanol	HPLC grade	Research Lab, Mumbai
3	Water	HPLC grade	Research Lab, Mumbai

5.1.2 Standard:

5.1.3 Table No. 4. Standard used

Sr.No.	Standard	Potency (%)
1	Dapagliflozin	99.99%

5.1.4 Sample:

Table No. 5. Sample used

Sr.No.	Sample	Make
1	Dapagliflozin	ChemicalBullPvt. Ltd. Gujarat.

Method Development

Preparation of Solutions (Sample and Standard)

Accurately weighed and transferred about 100 mg of Dapagliflozin standard into 100 ml volumetric flask and added diluent to dissolve and made up the volume with diluent. Further diluted 1 ml. of this solution to 100 mL with diluent.

TrialRun 1: Chromatographic conditions:

- Mobile Phase: Acetonitrile : Water(50 : 50 V/V)
- Column: Column C18 (Dimensions: 4.6 x 250 mm)
- Detection: 285 nm
- Injection volume: 10.0 μ L Column temperature: Ambient
- Flow rate: 0.8 mL/min
- Diluent: Water for HPLC
- Run time: 10 minutes.

Observation:

Dapagliflozin peak is not good; to get the good peak shape, next trial was taken by changing Mobile Phase ratio.

- Trial Run 2: Chromatographic conditions:
- Mobile Phase: Methanol: Acetonitrile (60 : 40 V/V)
- Column: Column C18 (Dimensions: 4.6 x 250 mm)
- Detection: 285 nm
- Injection volume: 10.0 μ L
- Column temperature: Ambient Flow rate: 1.0 mL/min
- Diluent: Water for HPLC
- Run time: 10 minutes

Trial Run 4: Chromatographic conditions:

- Mobile Phase: Acetonitrile : Water (75 : 25V/V)
- Column: Column C18 (Dimensions: 4.6 x 250 mm)
- Detection: 285 nm
- Injection volume: 10.0 μ L
- Column temperature: Ambient
- Flow rate: 1 mL/min
- Diluent: Water for HPLC
- Run time: 10 minutes

Observation:

Dapagliflozin peak is good and retention time is 3.323. The method is further considered for validation and routine analysis.

Figure No. 8. Typical Chromatogram of Diluent

Figure No. 9. Typical Chromatogram of Standard

Figure No. 10. Typical Chromatogram of Sample

Validation

System-suitability test are an integral part of method development and are used to ensure adequate performance of the chromatographic system. Retention time (Rt), Average (A), Standard Deviation (SD) and % RSD were evaluated for six replicate injection of the drug at a concentration of 30ug/ml.

Weigh and transferred the 100mg of Dapagliflozin in 100ml Volumetric Flask then mix well and dissolve and dilute with mobile phase. From this solution transfer the 0.3 ml into the 10ml of volumetric flask and make up the volume with mobile phase.

Preparation of Standard solution:

Accurately weighed and transferred about 100 mg of Dapagliflozin standard into 100 ml volumetric flask and added diluent to dissolve and made up the volume with diluent. Further diluted 1 ml. of this solution to 100 mL with diluent.

Preparation of Test solution:

Diluted 1 mL of sample to 10 mL. with diluent. Further diluted 2.5 mL of this solution to 100 mL. with diluent

Procedure:

□ Injected Diluent (Blank) (one injection), System suitability preparation (one injection), Standard preparation (Five injections), and check the system suitability parameters.

System suitability:

- The %RSD for five replicate injections of Standard preparation for Dapagliflozin should be NMT 2.0.
- Calculate the cumulative %RSD of Dapagliflozin peak for bracketing standard and should be NMT 2.0
- If System suitability passes, then inject Test preparation (two injections) and record the chromatograms,

5.5 Procedure:

The following parameters were considered for the Analytical method validation of Assay of Dapagliflozin in drug product Dapagliflozin.

- System suitability
- Specificity
- Forced degradation
- Precision
- System precision
- Method precision-Intermediate precision
- Stability in analytical solution
- Linearity
- Accuracy
- Range
- Robustness

5.5.1 System Suitability:

To verify that the analytical system is working properly and can give accurate and precise results, the system suitability parameters are to be set.

Injection profile:

Table No. 6. Injection Profile of System Suitability Acceptance criteria:

Sr.No	Sample	Number of injections
1	Diluent (Blank)	1
2	System suitability preparation	1
3	Standard preparation	5
4	Test preparation	2

The %RSD for five replicate injections of Standard preparation for Dapagliflozin should be NMT 2.0

5.5.3 Precision:

The precision of an analytical method is the degree of agreement among individual test results when the method is applied repeatedly to multiple sampling of homogeneous samples. The precision of analytical method is usually expressed as the standard deviation or relative standard deviation (Coefficient of variation) of series of measurements.

5.5.3.1 System Precision:

The system precision is checked by using standard chemical substances to ensure that the analytical system is working properly. The retention time and the area response of six determinations should be measured and calculated relative standard deviation.

Injection profile:

Injected separately each of the following solutions

Table No. 7. Injection Profile of System Precision

Solutions	Number of Injections
Diluent	1
Standard preparation	6

Acceptance criteria:

- The %RSD of the Retention time for the Dapagliflozin peak obtained from 6 injections of standard preparation should be NMT 1.0.
- The %RSD of the Area response for the Dapagliflozin peak obtained from 6 injections of standard preparation should be NMT 2.0.

5.5.3.3 Intermediate Precision:

- The intermediate precision is carried out in same laboratory to ensure that the analytical results will remain unaffected with change in analyst and day.
- Repeated the method precision set by other analyst using same column, instrument on different day. Calculated the % Assay of Dapagliflozin.
- Compared the results obtained in Method precision and Intermediate precision.

Acceptance criteria:

- The %RSD of the calculated Assay results for 6 determinations should be NMT 2.0.
- The %RSD of the calculated Assay results for 12 determinations (Method precision & Intermediate precision) should be NMT 2.0.

5.5.4 Stability in Analytical Solution:

Evaluated the stability in analytical solution by injecting the standard preparation and sample preparation at regular interval.

Acceptance criteria:

The % Difference of mean area response for the peaks in Standard preparation and Sample preparation should be within ± 2.0 from initial area after specified period.

5.5.5 Linearity:

- The linearity of an analytical method is its ability to elicit test results that are directly or by a well-defined mathematical transformation, proportional to the concentration of analyte in samples within a given range.

Performed the linearity with Dapagliflozin standard in the range of 20 to 70% (20%, 30%, 40%,

- 50%, 60%, and 70%) of specification limit.
- Recorded the area response for each level and calculated slope, intercept & correlation coefficient. Tested the intercept for statistical equivalence to zero.

- Also performed precision at lower and higher level by injecting 6 times into the chromatograph.
- Plotted a graph of Dapagliflozin standard concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$) on X-axis and Area response on Y-axis.

Weighed and transferred 100 mg of Dapagliflozin standard in 100 mL of volumetric flask Dissolved and diluted to volume with diluent and mixed well. Further diluted 5 mL of this solution to 10 mL.

Linearity Readings for Dapagliflozin:

Linearity Stock solution preparation:

Table No. 8. Linearity Readings for Dapagliflozin

Sr.No.	Dapagliflozin Conc. ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Dapagliflozin Area (mAU)
	0	0
1	20	115696
2	30	228696
3	40	339881
4	50	447719
5	60	554565
6	70	662056

Acceptance criteria:

- Correlation coefficient and Regression coefficient should be NLT 0.998.
- The % intercept should be within ± 5.0 of the Area response at 100% level.

5.5.6 Accuracy:

The accuracy of an analytical method is the closeness of test results obtained by that method to the true value (standard value). Spiked known quantity of Dapagliflozin standard at 80%, 100% and 120% of Assay specification limit. Analysed these samples in triplicate for each level. Calculated the % recovery from the results of Accuracy.

Accuracy stock solution:

- Weighed and transferred 100 mg of Dapagliflozin standard in 100 ml. of volumetric flask dissolved and diluted to volume with diluent and mixed well.

- Prepared the accuracy solutions with varying concentrations for the different recovery levels.

Table No. 9. Accuracy stock solution

Sr. No	Solutions
1	80 %
2	100 %
3	120 %

Acceptance criteria:

Individual and Mean % recovery for Dapagliflozin at each level should be between 96.0 and 103.0 % RSD at each accuracy level should be NMT 2.0.

5.5.8 Robustness:

The robustness of an analytical method is a measure of its capacity to remain unaffected by small but deliberate variations in method parameters and provides an indication of its reliability during normal usage.

Robustness parameters:

Change in flow rate ± 1 mL/min.

Injection profile: Injected each of the following solutions into the system by change in flow rate.

Table No. 10. Injection Profile of Robustness

Solutions	Number of Injection
Diluent	1
Standard solution	5

Acceptance criteria:

The RSD of the Area response for the Dapagliflozin peak obtained from 5 injections of standard preparation should be NMT 2.0

5.6 Formulae for Calculation: Correlation Coefficient (r):

$$r = \frac{n(\sum xy) - (\sum x)(\sum y)}{\sqrt{[n\sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2][n\sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2]}}$$

Σ = Sum of x = Conc. of the Component, y = Avg. Area response ratio of component,

n = number of observations

($n \sum XY - \sum X \sum Y$)

a) Slope (a) = ($n \sum X^2 - \sum (X)^2$)

b) The equation of straight line: $Y = aX + b$

c) Tailing factor (T): $T = (a+b)/2a$

d) Resolution (R_s) = $2(t-t_1)/w_1+w_2$

t₂: Retention time of peak (2)

t₁: Retention time of peak (1)

w₂: Peak width at the base line of peak (2) w₁: Peak width at the base line of peak (1)

f) Intercept on the Y axis (b) = $Y - aX$, (X = mean values of X), (Y = mean values of Y)

g) Calculate the Assay of Dapagliflozin by using the following formula.

AT WS DT P 100 408.9

% Assay = $\frac{AS \cdot DS \cdot VT \cdot 100 \cdot LC}{AT \cdot WS \cdot DT \cdot P \cdot 408.9}$

AS DS VT 100 LC 408.9

Where,

AT: Average Area of Dapagliflozin peak obtained from chromatogram of assay preparation.

AS: Average Area of Dapagliflozin peak obtained from chromatogram of Standard preparation

WS: Weight of Dapagliflozin standard in mg

DS: Dilution of Standard preparation

DT: Dilution of test preparation

VT: Volume of Sample taken in ml.

P: Potency of Dapagliflozin standard

LC: Label claim Dapagliflozin in [mg/mL]

408.9 : Molecular weight of Dapagliflozin

OBSERVATION AND RESULT

1.1 System Suitability:

Table No. 11. Results for System Suitability

Sr.No.	Ret. Time (MIN)	Area Response
1	3.357	141811
2	3.352	138841
3	3.356	141960
4	3.351	140624
5	3.334	140533

Average	3.351	140649.33
SD	0.009	1285.31642
%RSD	0.27	0.913844

System Suitability Chromatogram

Data interpretation:

From the above results, it can be concluded that the system is suitable for analytical method validation.

1.1 Precision:

1.1.1 System Precision:

Table No. 12. Results for System Precision

Sr.No.	Ret. Time(MIN)	Area Response
1	3.312	134504
2	3.314	135259
3	3.338	135015
4	3.337	133062
5	3.324	134025
6	3.341	132015
Average	3.327	133980
SD	0.01	1239.96
%RSD	0.38	0.92

Following are the system precision Chromatograms(5Chromatograms)

Data Interpretation:

From the above results, it can be concluded that Retention time & Area response are consistent as evidenced by Relative standard deviation. Hence, it is concluded that the system precision parameters meets the requirement of Method validation.

From the statistical treatment of linearity data interpretation of Dapagliflozin, it is clear that the response of Dapagliflozin is linear between 20 to 70% level of specification limit. The correlation & regression coefficient is 0.9931.

1.2 Accuracy:

Data Interpretation:

Accuracy Reading For 80% of Dapagliflozin

Conc. In PPM	Rt. of Dapagliflozin	Peak area of Dapagliflozin	Recovery
50+40	3.294	389033	96.06
50+40	3.203	389249	96.17
50+40	3.304	389445	96.27
Avg	3.267	389242.3333	96.16667
SD	0.05650696	206.808903	0.10504
%RSD	1.7	0.1	0.1

Accuracy 80% of Dapagliflozin Chromatogram

Accuracy Reading For 100% of Dapagliflozin

Conc. In PPM	Rt of Dapagliflozin	Peak area of Dapagliflozin	Recovery
50+50	3.302	394023	98.58
50+50	3.286	394569	98.85
50+50	3.303	395054	99.09
Avg	3.297	394548.7	98.84
SD	0.009539392	515.8007	0.255147016
%RSD	0.3	0.1	0.3

Accuracy 100% of Dapagliflozin Chromatogram

Accuracy reading for 120% of Dapagliflozin

Conc. In PPM	Rt of Dapagliflozin	Peak area of Dapagliflozin	Recovery
50+60	3.245	402234	102.70
50+60	3.256	405338	102.71
50+60	3.229	406234	104.7
Avg	3.24333333	404602	103.37
SD	0.13576941	2099.112193	1.151825
%RSD	0.4	0.5	1.1

Accuracy 120% of Dapagliflozin Chromatogram

Figure No. 12. Accuracy of Dapagliflozin

Data Interpretation:

From the above results, it can be concluded that the recovery is well within the limit. Hence, the Method is accurate.

Accurately weighed and transferred about 100 mg of Dapagliflozin standard into 100 ml volumetric flask and added diluent to dissolve and made up the volume with diluent. Further diluted 1 ml of this solution.

ROBUSTNESS

1.1 Robustness:

Table No.16. Results for Robustness change in flow rate and Wavelength

Parameter	Modification	RT	Peak Area	Average	SD	%RSD
Flow rate	0.9	3.581	146254			
		3.582	143253	144177.3333	1802.055586	1.2
		3.58	143025			
	1	3.297	140753			
		3.211	143986	142489	1629.697211	1.1
		3.225	142728			
	1.1	3.041	61235			
		3.044	61542	61433.33333	172.0242231	0.3
		3.041	61523			
Change in mobile phase	70:30	3.236	151483			
		3.344	152314	152283	784.9592346	0.5
		3.451	153052			
	75:25	3.357	141811			
		3.356	141960	141299.3333	1018.000164	0.7
		3.351	140127			
	80:20	3.352	76021			
		3.321	76521	76397.66667	332.6158946	0.4
		3.343	76651			

Robustness Chromatogram (change in Flow Rate)

Robustness Chromatogram (change in Mobile phase)

Data Interpretation:

From the above results, it can be concluded that the Method is robust.

CONCLUSION

As this method is official in USP and used for Dapagliflozin formulation hence taken from USP and applied for the solid formulation of Dapagliflozin and proves that method hold good by performing the precision study, accuracy, and linearity. Based upon these results the method has been finalized and moving for validation of the same.

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